

RESEARCH PROJECT MANAGEMENT

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INtegration and Digital demonstration of low-emission aircraft technoloGies and airport Operations

INDIGO

**Work package: WP4 - Models for airport LAQ&N performance and
operations**

**Preliminary Deliverable: D4.1 Extended Airport Operations and
Performance Model**

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1 Introduction

This document is a preliminary version for the Deliverable 4.1 within WP4 Models for airport LAQ&N performance and operations. The main objective is to describe the work done in T4.1 Selection of airports and operations scenario. For this purpose, the following points will be explained in the document sections:

1. Selection of Use Cases (airports for study)
2. Baseline scenarios description including:
 - a. Terrain and meteorological data
 - b. Airport terminal and runway/stands configuration.
 - c. Traffic demand and type
 - d. Procedures (SID/STAR profiles)
3. Identification of the applicable regulatory framework of the Use Cases to address emissions and noise from aircraft engines and propagation in the vicinity of the airport.
4. LAQ&N key performance indicators (LAQ&N- KPI) applicable to the Use Cases.
5. Critical pollutants of LAQ for each Use Case.

This work intends to establish an operational environment for the following tasks within WP4 and for WP5 and WP6 in terms of optimization setup and validation.

This document will be updated with new inputs from T4.2 for the D4.1 final delivery.

2 Use Case Selection

This section will explain the methodology followed to select the most relevant Use Cases for the validation of INDIGO solution. Each of the Use Cases will consist of a characteristic European airport.

2.1 Methodology for selection

The steps to be achieved for the final selection of the use cases is as follows:

1. General selection of most interesting and/or representative European airports: up to 68 airports.
2. Define and fill variables as the main characteristics for each airport, with the following criteria:
 - a. Traffic volume: Big (>20M), Medium (5M-20M), Small (<5M)
 - b. Terrain: flat (relative altitude difference <200 m and 15 km from start of roll), mountain (>+200 m and 15 km from start of roll), next to the sea, inland
 - c. Atmospheric and meteorology information: summer (sunny, dry), winter (rainy, windy, stormy).
 - i. Hot, monthly temperature above 25
 - ii. Cold, less than 0
 - iii. Warm, monthly temperature between 20 - 25
 - iv. Mild, monthly temperature not above 20
 - v. Dry, less than 20 mm
 - vi. Wet, more than 100 mm
 - vii. Very wet, more than 200 mm
 - d. Population exposure: nearby airport, under flight path
 - e. Runway configuration: single, multiple and crossing
 - f. Country economic category (eg. GDP): Medium (<20k), Medium-High (20k-50k), High (>50k)
 - g. Data availability/limitation: Full, Partial, None
3. Preselection (top 13) of the most relevant use cases in terms of the variables listed for each use case. Criteria used:
 - a. Airport representativeness in terms of recognition and movements
 - b. Complementarity of the selected airports between them in terms of the listed characteristics so that the final use cases cover the maximum

spectrum of the variables listed. The objective is to validate with INDIGO solution all representative/possible airport operational and environmental frameworks.

- c. The availability/access to the data for each airport. The content, accuracy and level of detail that can be obtained.
- 4. Final selection of the use cases (4 candidates) considering mainly the complementarity and data access.

2.2 Selection of Use Cases

Following the methodology proposed in previous section, 68 airports are under study (see Figure 1 as example). From this list, the 13 most interesting and likely available use cases are selected (see Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Airport	Country	City	Traffic volume	Female	Female	Atmospheric and meteorology	Population affected	Remedy Configuration	Country (GDP, mortality)	Data availability (ENR movement)
Melbourne	Australia	Melbourne	17,000,000	102 m	102 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Sydney Kingsford Smith	Australia	Sydney	40,000,000	6 m	6 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Parallel and crossing	\$13,819	
Brussels	Belgium	Brussels	3,500	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$42,459	
See Paulo Guarulhos	Brazil	Guarulhos	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$1,840	1287
Johannesburg	Belgium	Johannesburg	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Arturo Merino Benítez	Chile	Santiago	2000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
El Dorado	Colombia	Bogotá	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Dagoberto Frangić Tuđman Airport	Croatia	Zagreb	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Larnaca	Cyprus	Larnaca	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Paphos	Cyprus	Paphos	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Prague - Václav Havel	Czech	Prague	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Tallinn Airport	Estonia	Tallinn	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Enontekiö	Finland	Enontekiö	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Oulu	Finland	Oulu	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Kuopio	Finland	Kuopio	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Marseille-Méditerranée	France	Marseille	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Paris-Orly	France	Paris	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	
Frankfurt	Germany	Frankfurt	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold 17° max. Some rain 1.8 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Some rain 2.7 inches. Partly clear & cloudy. Windy 9.8 (1). Cool 17° max. Mostly clear. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Very cold 17° max. Comfortable 27° max. Rainy 4 (1). Comfortable 27° max. Windy 8.8 mph (6). Partly cloudy. Windy 22.2 mph. Very cold 17° max.	Very low. Isolated houses at the extension of the airport.	Crossing	\$13,819	

Figure 1 General UC selection

Airport	Country	City	Traffic volume	Female	Female	Atmospheric and meteorology	Population affected	Remedy Configuration	Country (GDP, mortality)	Data availability (ENR movement)
Sofia Airport	Bulgaria	Sofia	1000	100 m	100 m	Warm summers. Cold winters.	Low approach high	Crossing	\$12,000	
Rome Ciampino	Italy	Ciampino (Lido)	1000	100 m	100 m	Warm summers. Mild winters.	Very high approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Riga International Airport	Latvia	Riga	1000	100 m	100 m	Mild summers. Cold winters.	Medium low approach	Crossing	\$12,000	
Bergen Flesland	Norway	Bergen	1000	100 m	100 m	Mild summers. Mild very wet winters.	Low approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Oslo Gardermoen	Norway	Gardermoen	1000	100 m	100 m	Mild summers. Cold winters.	Medium low approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Humberto Delgado Airport	Portugal	Lisbon	1000	100 m	100 m	Very hot summers. Warm winters.	Medium high approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Alcántara	Spain	Alcántara	1000	100 m	100 m	Very hot summers. Warm winters.	Medium low approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Batolona El Prat	Spain	Batolona	1000	100 m	100 m	Very hot summers. Warm winters.	Medium high approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Adolfo Suárez Madrid-Barajas	Spain	Madrid	1000	100 m	100 m	Very hot summers. Warm winters.	Medium high approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Tenerife Norte - Ciudad de la Legión (Los Rodeos)	Spain	Tenerife	1000	100 m	100 m	Warm dry summers. Warm winters.	Medium low high approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Stockholm Arlanda	Sweden	Stockholm	1000	100 m	100 m	Mild summers. Cold winters.	Very low approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Salzburg Airport	Austria	Salzburg	1000	100 m	100 m	Mild wet summer. Mild winter.	Medium low approach	Crossing	\$10,000	
Dortmund Airport	Germany	Dortmund	1000	100 m	100 m	Cold winters.	Medium approach	Crossing	\$10,000	

Figure 2 Top 13 selected UC

The top 13 airports are:

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Airport	Country	City
Sofia Airport	Bulgaria	Sofia
Roma-Ciampino	Italy	Ciampino (Lazio)
Riga International Airport	Latvia	Riga
Bergen Flesland	Norway	Bergen
Oslo Gardermoen	Norway	Gardermoen
Humberto Delgado Airport	Portugal	Lisbon
Alicante	Spain	Alicante
Barcelona El Prat	Spain	Barcelona
Adolfo Suárez Madrid Baraja	Spain	Madrid
Tenerife Norte - Ciudad de la Laguna (Los Rodeos)	Spain	Tenerife
Stockholm Arlanda	Sweden	Sigtuna Municipality
Salzburg Airport	Austria	Salzburg
Dortmund Airport	Germany	Dortmund

Figure 3 Top 13 airports

Eventually, the final 4 Use Cases are selected:

Airport	Country	City	Traffic volume			Terrain			Atmospheric and meteorological conditions			Population affected by airport flight per year	Runway Configuration	Country (GDP, mortality)			Data availability							
			Big (>20M)	Medium (5M-20M)	Small (<5M)	flat	mountain	next to the sea	inland	summer (sunny)	rainy			winter (windy)	Low	Medium	High	Single	Multiple and crossing	Medium	High	Very High	Full	Partial
Riga Intern	Latvia	Riga		6M		flat		10.5 M		mild summers	Cold winters	Medium low encroachment	Medium encroachment					21167						
Barcelona El Prat	Spain	Barcelona	42 M			flat		4.0 M		Dry hot summers	Warm winters	Low encroachment	Medium encroachment		2 parallel and 1 crossing			30058						
Adolfo Suárez Madrid Baraja	Spain	Madrid	60 M			flat		610	172 M	Hot dry summers	Mild winters	Medium encroachment	Medium encroachment		2+2 paralel			30058						
Dortmund	Germany	Dortmund			2M		129				Cold winters	Medium encroachment	Medium encroachment					48845						

Figure 4 Final 4 UC

This final selection is meeting the following criteria:

- Representativeness from different countries: Spain, Latvia and Germany.
- All airport categories: small, medium and big airports.
- All types of terrain: flat, mountain and sea/inland.
- All meteorologic conditions: summer and winter seasonal characteristics.

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- Population exposure maximized: either next the to airport or under the flight path. In order to maximize the representativeness of the LAQ&N benefit expected from INDIGO.
- All types of runway configurations: single and multiple with parallel or crossing runways.
- The most frequent/representative GDP medium category 20k to 50k.
- All data access available due to either partnership from the project (Madrid, Barcelona and Riga airports with full access and maximum granularity) or external invitation and data protection agreement (Dortmund airport with also almost full access).

These 4 use cases will be described in detail in the following sections as expected to be the validation scenarios for the INDIGO solution.

Note: full table of use cases available in Annex A.

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3 Baseline scenarios

3.1 Terrain and meteorological information

The following sections present the information related to terrain, obstacles, meteorological parameters for each of the selected Use Cases.

3.1.1 Dortmund

Altitude of Airport is 425 ft and terrain around Airport is between 68 and 172 m elevation.

Figure 5 Obstacles map for DTM airport

The following figure shows an example of a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) with a 1-meter resolution that covers the airport and surroundings. These models are expected to be used for the LAQ&N assessment and will validate the influence of the terrain both in noise and pollutant dispersion.

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Figure 6 Terrain model for DTM airport

Month 2022	Wind speed (m/s)			Wind Direction (°)	Temperature (°C)			Hum. (%)			Air Pressure (mBar)		
	Min	Max	Avg		Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg	Min	Max	Avg
January	0	11,8	4,2	225	-2	14	4,2	53	100	88	987	1041	1023
February	0	17,5	6,5	225	-3	13	6	30	100	77	990	1035	1015
March	0	10,8	3,1	75	-4	19	7,4	20	100	60	998	1044	1023
April	0	13,4	3,8	0	-2	23	9	25	100	69	981	1033	1014
May	0	10,3	3,1	0	4	28	14,8	37	100	68	996	1028	1017
June	0	9,3	3	0	6	32	18,1	28	100	68	1006	1024	1016
July	0	7,2	2,7	0	9	38	19,5	11	100	62	1008	1031	1020
August	0	6,2	2,4	0	8	34	21,3	21	100	60	1003	1028	1017
September	0	9,8	3,1	0	5	30	14,8	27	100	74	994	1027	1012
October	0	9,8	3,8	195	4	24	13,9	45	100	79	1002	1030	1018
November	0	9,8	4,2	195	-5	16	8,8	50	100	79	989	1032	1012
December	0	14,9	4,3	225	-8	17	3,7	41	100	85	999	1028	1013

Table 1 Meteorological information for DTM

3.1.2 Riga

Altitude of Airport is 11 m and terrain around Airport is mostly flat. Within 20 km highest altitude is 28 m for natural features. There is recultivated garbage hill with altitude 36 m. Most of natural terrain features are dunes and, in most cases, they are covered by pine forest.

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Obstacle map (all obstacles above 1,2% gradient form threshold) is shown in Figure 7:

Figure 7: RIX airport obstacle map

The following figure shows an example of a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) with a 20-meter resolution that covers all the Latvian terrain. These models are expected to be used for the LAQ&N assessment and will validate the influence of the terrain both in noise and pollutant dispersion.

Figure 8 Example of Digital Terrain Model (DTM) for RIX

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The following table shows the average meteorological parameters for RIX airport during year of study.

Parameter	Wind Speed	Temp.	Hum.	Air Pressure	Dewpoint	Gust	Visibility
	[m/s]	[°C]	[%]	[mBar]	[°C]	[m/s]	[m]
Min	0.5	-16.0	20.0	962.0			258.0
Average	3.3	7.8	79.2	1014.0			9395.5
Max	14.4	32.0	100.0	1048.0		23.7	9999.0
0.01	0.5	-9.0	32.0	980	-12.0	0.0	998
0.05	1.0	-5.0	43.0	993	-8.0	0.0	4508
0.1	1.0	-3.0	51.0	999	-6.0	0.0	8002
0.2	1.5	0.0	63.0	1006	-3.0	0.0	9999
0.3	2.1	2.0	72.0	1010	-1.0	0.0	9999
0.4	2.6	4.0	80.0	1013	1.0	0.0	9999
0.5	3.1	8.0	86.0	1015	4.0	0.0	9999
0.6	3.6	10.0	88.0	1017	7.0	0.0	9999
0.7	4.1	12.0	93.0	1019	9.0	0.0	9999
0.8	4.6	15.0	93.0	1022	11.0	0.0	9999
0.9	6.2	20.0	100.0	1027	15.0	0.0	9999
0.95	7.2	23.0	100.0	1032	17.0	0.0	9999
0.99	9.3	29.0	100.0	1041	19.0	13.4	9999

Table 2 Meteorological information for RIX

Figure 9: Wind rose of RIX airport

3.1.3 Barcelona

Altitude of Airport is 4 m and terrain around Airport is mostly flat.

Figure 10 Obstacle map for BCN airport

The following figure shows an example of a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) with a 25-meter resolution (from the Spanish Geographic Institute) that covers the airport and surroundings. These models are expected to be used for the LAQ&N assessment and will validate the influence of the terrain both in noise and pollutant dispersion.

Figure 11 Terrain data for BCN airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Parameter	knots	gustyWind	visibility	temperature	dewPoint	qnh
Min	0	0	150	1	-15	995
Average	7		9630	17	12	1017
Max	28	1	9999	33	25	1035
0.01	0	0	3000	3.78	-3	1000
0.05	2	0	7000	7	1	1006
0.1	3	0	9000	9	3	1009
0.2	4	0	9999	12	7	1013
0.3	5	0	9999	13	9	1014
0.4	6	0	9999	15	10	1016
0.5	7	0	9999	18	12	1017
0.6	8	0	9999	20	15	1019
0.7	9	0	9999	22	17	1020
0.8	11	0	9999	24	19	1023
0.9	13	0	9999	27	21	1026
0.95	15	0	9999	28	22	1028
0.99	20	1	9999	30	24	1032

Table 3 Meteorological information for BCN airport

Figure 12 Wind rose for BCN airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

3.1.4 Madrid

Altitude of Airport is 609 m and terrain around Airport is between 440 m and 1606 m elevation.

Figure 13 Obstacles map for MAD airport

The following figure shows an example of a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) with a 25-meter resolution (from the Spanish Geographic Institute) that covers the airport and surroundings. These models are expected to be used for the LAQ&N assessment and will validate the influence of the terrain both in noise and pollutant dispersion.

Figure 14 Terrain data for MAD airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Parameter	knots	gustyWind	visibility	temperature	dewPoint	qnh
Min	0	0	100	-5	-12	997
Average	4		9103	16	6	1018
Max	28	1	9999	42	19	1035
0.01	0	0	900	-2	-7	1002
0.05	1	0	4000	2	-3	1009
0.1	1	0	6000	5	0	1011
0.2	2	0	9999	8	2	1014
0.3	3	0	9999	11	4	1016
0.4	3	0	9999	13	5	1017
0.5	4	0	9999	15	7	1018
0.6	5	0	9999	18	8	1020
0.7	6	0	9999	22	9	1021
0.8	7	0	9999	26	10	1023
0.9	10	0	9999	30	12	1027
0.95	12	0	9999	35	13	1029
0.99	16	1	9999	39	16	1031

Table 4 Meteorological information for MAD airport

Figure 15 Wind rose for MAD airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

3.2 Terminal information

The sections below present the terminal map, the runways and taxiways structure and the stand location for each Use Case.

3.2.1 Dortmund

Dortmund has a single runway with direction 06/24. The location of the runway, taxiways, stands, terminal and other buildings are shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Infrastructure of Dortmund Airport.

3.2.2 Riga

RIX has one runway with directions 18 and 36. Runway, taxiways, stands, terminal, and other buildings is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Infrastructure of Riga International Airport.

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3.2.3 Barcelona

BCN has three runways in total. Two runways are parallel to each other with directions 06/24 and the third runway is crossing one of the parallel with directions 02/20. Runways, taxiways, stands, terminal (separate) and other buildings are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Infrastructure of Barcelona Josep Tarradellas Barcelona-El Prat Airport.

3.2.4 Madrid

Madrid airport has four two-by-two parallel runways. The runways further north have directions 18/36 with specific name of 18L/36R for the right-hand runway and 18R/36L for the left-hand runway. The other two parallel runways with directions 14/32 have the same nomenclature as the other one, the left one is 14R/32L and the right one is 14L/32R. The runways, taxiways, stands, terminals (T123, T4 and T4S) and other buildings are shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Infrastructure of Adolfo Suárez Madrid-Barajas Airport.

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3.3 Traffic demand and aircraft type information

3.3.1 Traffic demand volumes

An analysis has been conducted for medium wake aircraft, using as a sample the flights that took place throughout the entirety of 2022 to obtain the data.

3.3.1.1 Dortmund

The following charts illustrates the annual statistics of the departures and arrivals of flights at the airport of Dortmund. Each bar on the graph represents a month and shows the volume of flights during that period. This comprehensive data is intended to provide an overview of flight activity throughout the year, making it easier to understand traffic patterns and trends at the airport.

In the case of this airport, most of the operations are flown with light wake aircraft, so there is a smaller sample compared to the other cases for medium wake analysis.

Figure 20 Departures per month for DTM airport in 2022

Figure 21 Arrivals per month for DTM airport in 2022

3.3.1.2 Riga

The following charts illustrates the annual statistics of the departures and arrivals of flights at the airport of Riga. This comprehensive data is intended to provide an overview of flight activity throughout the year, making it easier to understand traffic patterns and trends at the airport.

Figure 22 Departures per month for RIX airport in 2022

Figure 23 Arrivals per month for RIX airport in 2022

3.3.1.3 Barcelona

For Barcelona Airport, a comprehensive analysis was conducted to identify the trends in arrivals and departures throughout 2022, as with previous airport assessments. At the beginning of the year, there was a decline in the number of flights due to the continuing impact of COVID, but then the previous demand started to recover.

Figure 24 Departures per month for BCN airport in 2022

Figure 25 Arrivals per month for BCN airport in 2022

3.3.1.4 Madrid

For Madrid Airport, a comprehensive analysis was conducted to identify the trends in arrivals and departures throughout 2022, as with previous airport assessments. As in Barcelona airport, the impact of COVID on Madrid airport is observed during the first few months.

Figure 26 Departures per month for MAD airport in 2022

Figure 27 Arrivals per month for MAD airport in 2022

3.3.2 Aircraft type

Due to differences in distance and demand, certain aircraft models may be more commonly used for one type of flight over the other. Here are the most common aircraft models for each type of flight in Europe:

- **International:**
 - BCS3 (A220-300):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	35.1 m
Length	38.7 m
Height	11.5 m
Power Plant	2 x PurePower PW1500G (85-125 kN)
OTHERS	
Passengers	160 + 2 flightcrew

Table 5: BCS3 (A220-300) profile

Figure 28 BCS3 (A220-300) performance

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▪ B738 (B737-800):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	D
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	34.4 m
Length	39.2 m
Height	12.6 m
Power Plant	2 x 117 kN CFMI CFM56-7B turbofans
OTHERS	
Passengers	162 + 2 flightcrew

Table 6 B738 (B737-800) profile

Figure 29 B738 (B737-800) performance

▪ A320:

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	34.1 m
Length	37.57 m
Height	11.76 m
Power Plant	2 x 111 kN CFM56-5A1 or 2 x 118 kN CFM56-5A3 or 2 x 125 kN IAE V2500 turbofans
OTHERS	
Passengers	150-180 + 2 flightcrew

Table 7 A320 profile

Figure 30 A320 performance

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- B38M (B737 MAX 8):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	D
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	35.09 m
Length	39.52 m
Height	12.29 m
Power Plant	2 x CFM International LEAP-1B (130 kN) turbofans
OTHERS	
Passengers	210 + 2 flight crew

Table 8 B38M (B737 MAX 8) profile

Figure 31 B38M (B737 MAX 8) performance

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▪ A321:

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	34.1 m
Length	44.51 m
Height	11.76 m
Power Plant	2 x 133 kN CFM56-5B1 or 2 x 133 kN IAE V2530-A5 turbofans
OTHERS	
Passengers	180-210 + 2 flight crew

Table 9 A321 profile

Figure 32 A321 performance

- A20N (A320 Neo):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	35.8 m
Length	37.57 m
Height	11.76 m
Power Plant	2 x 120.6 kN CFM International LEAP-1A or Pratt & Whitney PW1100G
OTHERS	
Passengers	Same as A320

Table 10 A20N (A320 Neo) profile

Figure 33 A20N (A320 Neo) performance

- A319:

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	34.1 m
Length	33.84 m
Height	11.76 m
Power Plant	2 x 98 kN CFM56-5A4 or 2 x 104.6 kN IAE V2524-A5 turbofans
OTHERS	
Passengers	124-142 + 2 flight crew

Table 11: A319 profile

Figure 34 A319 performance

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

▪ CRJX:

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2J
Category	C
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	26.18 m
Length	39.13 m
Height	7.5 m
Power Plant	2 x GE CF34-8C5A1 (64.5kN)
OTHERS	
Passengers	86-104 + 2 flight crew

Table 12: CRJX profile

Figure 35: CRJX performance.

○ **Domestic:**

The aircraft used for international flights can also use for domestic flights.

- AT75 (ATR-72-500):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2T
Category	B
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	27.05 m
Length	27.17 m
Height	7.65 m
Power Plant	2 x 2500 SHP PWC PW127F turboprops with 6 blade propellers
OTHERS	
Passengers	68-78 + 2 flight crew

Table 13 AT75 (ATR-72-500) profile

Figure 36 AT75 (ATR-72-500) performance

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▪ AT76 (ATR-72-600):

AIRCRAFT TYPE	
Type	L2T
Category	B
WTC	M
TECHNICAL SKILLS	
Wingspan	27.05 m
Length	27.17 m
Height	7.65 m
Power Plant	2 x 2700 SHP PWC PW127XT-M turboprops with 6 blade propellers
OTHERS	
Passengers	68-78 + 2 flight crew

Table 14 AT76 (ATR-72-600) profile

ENGINES	
Pratt & Whitney Canada	PW127XT-M
Power	2,750 SHP

WEIGHTS		
Max take-off weight	23,000 kg	50,705 lb
Max landing weight	22,350 kg	49,272 lb
Max zero fuel weight	21,000 kg	46,296 lb
Operational empty weight (typical in-service)	13,600 kg	29,983 lb
Max payload	7,400 kg	16,313 lb
Max fuel load	5,000 kg	11,024 lb

AIRFIELD PERFORMANCE

Take-off field length		
> @ MTOW - ISA - Sea Level	1,315 m	4,314 ft
> @ TOW for 300 NM - Max Pax - ISA +10 - Sea Level ⁽¹⁾	1,140 m	3,740 ft
Landing field length		
> @ MLW - ISA - Sea Level (EASA Air Ops)	915 m	3,002 ft

EN-ROUTE PERFORMANCE

Climb speed	170 KCAS	
Max cruise speed (95% MTOW - ISA - FL200)	270 KTAS	500 km/h
Fuel consumption in cruise (95% MTOW - ISA - FL200)	650 kg/h	1432 lb/h
One engine-out net ceiling (95% MTOW - ISA +10)	2,990 m	9,800 ft
Range with max pax ⁽¹⁾	740 NM	1,370 km

Standard routes ⁽²⁾	200 NM	300 NM	400 NM
Block fuel	624 kg - 1,376 lb	869 kg - 1,916 lb	1,115 kg - 2,458 lb
CO ₂ emissions	1.97 t	2.75 t	3.52 t
Block time	01:02	01:24	01:47

ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE

CO ₂ per seat/km ⁽³⁾	69 g	0.15 lb
NOx per Landing and Take-off cycle	2.6 kg	5.7 lb
Noise certification (ICAO Ch 14) margin ⁽⁴⁾⁽⁵⁾	-5.1 EPNdB	

Figure 37 AT76 (ATR-72-600) performance

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

3.3.2.1 Dortmund

Over the course of an entire year at Dortmund Airport, the utilisation rates of different aircraft types paint a revealing picture of the aviation landscape in this specific airport. Analysing the percentage of aircraft used over an extended period provides insights into the operational dynamics and preference. Looking at the data for the most common aircraft types outlined above, the percentages represent the frequency with which these aircraft are active and the type of aircraft most use that indicated the traffic trends and patterns.

In this case, medium-wake aircraft account for **44%** of flights at this airport, as it is a small airport, and these aircraft are not used as frequently as light aircrafts.

There are some aircraft that appear in this table that are not covered in the previous section (e.g., A21N), but they correspond to smaller percentages, and it has been decided not to include their performance.

Dortmund	
Aircraft	%
A320	24%
B738	8%
A321	3%
A21N	2%
E55P	1%
A20N	1%
B38M	1%
A319	1%

Table 15 Aircraft type frequency for DTM airport

3.3.2.2 Riga

In contrast to the previous airport, Riga airport has a **93%** utilisation rate of medium wake aircraft, half of the total flights being operated with aircrafts BCS3. The performance of the most commonly used aircrafts in this airport are shown above.

Riga	
Aircraft	%
BCS3	50%
B738	21%
A320	5%
AT75	4%
B38M	3%
B734	2%
F100	2%
A319	2%
DH8D	1%
A321	1%
A20N	1%

Table 16 Aircraft type frequency for RIX airport

3.3.2.3 Barcelona

As in the previous airport, Barcelona airport has a **94%** utilisation rate of medium wake aircraft, almost half of the total flights being operated with aircrafts A320. The performance of the most used aircrafts in this airport are shown above.

Barcelona	
Aircraft	%
A320	39%
B738	24%
A20N	12%
A321	11%
A319	7%
A21N	2%
B38M	1%

Table 17 Aircraft type frequency for BCN airport

3.3.2.4 Madrid

For Madrid airport, the percentage of use of medium wake aircraft is **86%**. In this case, the use of different aircraft models is more distributed among the most used aircraft in general aviation. The performance of the most used aircrafts in this airport are shown above.

Madrid	
Aircraft	%
B738	27%
A320	23%
CRJX	12%
A321	10%
A20N	8%
A319	6%
A21N	5%

Table 18 Aircraft type frequency for MAD airport

There are RNP AR approaches developed at DTM, which are the shortest approaches. The next two figures are for RNP arrivals (STARs) for both runways.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Real data of flights that have departed and arrived at DTM airport have been processed. Average values have been obtained to observe the profile of the aircraft for a range of altitude for ground speed and vertical speed at certain points in vertical profile and the mean trajectory in lateral profile. The data are taken from the entire 2022 year.

Figure 42 Departure vertical flight profiles for DTM airport

RUNWAY 06			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.30	500	134	2008
0.72	1000	148	3435
2.31	2000	170	1823
3.79	3000	168	2304
RUNWAY 24			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.29	500	131	1862
0.61	1000	139	3586
1.99	2000	171	1948
3.35	3000	171	2380

Table 19 Departure vertical flight profiles for DTM airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 43 Arrival vertical flight profiles for DTM airport

RUNWAY 06				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
3000ft	8.96	3000	166	879
FAF	7.20	2500	135	789
FA 2000ft	5.19	2000	150	701
FA 1000ft	1.93	1000	131	1158
LD 500ft	0.63	500	213	705
RUNWAY 24				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
FAF	7.7	3000	143	1380
FA 2000ft	5.11	2000	140	729
FA 1000ft	1.87	1000	129	1208
LD 500ft	0.58	500	215	691

Table 20 Arrival vertical flight profiles for DTM airport

Figure 44 Global lateral flight profiles for DTM airport

Figure 45 Departure lateral flight profiles for DTM airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 46 Arrival lateral flight profiles for DTM airport

3.4.2 Riga

Departing procedures can be classified in 3 groups: “F” type – departure to south, “H” type – departure to north and “J” type – departure to north with early turn to West. ATC almost always allows directs to waypoint before procedure stipulates turn to waypoint. It normally happens after aircraft has reached 3000 ft. See procedures in figures.

Figure 47: "F" type departures to east

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 48: "F" type departures to west

Figure 49: "H" type departures to east

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 50: "H" type departures to west

Figure 51: "J" type departures

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

There are RNP AR approaches developed at RIX, which are the shortest approaches, but is only used by one carrier, which have aircraft capable to fly the procedures. The procedures require capability to fly RF leg.

Figure 52: RNP AR approaches from south

Figure 53: RNP AR approaches from north

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

There are ILS approaches, they have a T-bar and most of arrival aircraft uses these approaches:

Figure 54: ILS T-bar approaches from south

Figure 55: ILS T-bar approaches from north

There are RNP approaches developed, which are identical to ILS approaches.

Figure 56: RNP T-bar approaches from south

Figure 57: RNP T-bar approaches from north

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Aircraft normally when fly STARS are above 3000 feet, exceptions are when they arrive from north or south and are already aligned to the runway. Additionally, some STARS from west terminates at altitude 2500 feet.

Figure 58: STARS from south

Figure 59: STARS from north

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 60: STARS from west

Real data of flights that have departed and arrived at RIX airport have been processed. Average values have been obtained to observe the profile of the aircraft for a range of altitude for ground speed and vertical speed at certain points in vertical profile and the mean trajectory in lateral profile. The data are taken from the entire 2022 year.

For departure procedures, the data is represented for both thresholds, runway 18 and runway 36. The data used to represent the graph has also been added and is found in the following table.

Figure 61 Rix departures performance

RUNWAY 18				RUNWAY 36			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
1.05	139	139	866.5	1.15	126.2	134.8	525.0
1.55	524	144	2364	1.55	551.0	139.5	2568.5
2	1070.5	144.5	2522.5	2.15	1100.9	141.4	2694.9
3.05	2058	147	2192.5	3.05	2011.3	145.1	2312.1
4.2	3006	151.5	2031	4.15	2972.5	150.1	2060.8
5.9	4001	168.5	1642	5.75	3994.5	171.5	1706.3
7.65	4956.5	196	1954	7.7	4967.2	207.6	2086.1
9.4	6014	232	2407.5	9.35	5951.0	233.4	2465.2

Table 21. Rix departure performance data.

For arrivals procedures, the data is also represented for both thresholds, runway 18 and runway 36. In this case, the representative points are the IF (Intermediate Approach Point), FAP (Final Approach Point), FA (for Final Approach at 2000ft and 1000ft) and LD (Landing at 500ft and at the runway). The data used to represent the graph has also been added and is found in the following table.

Figure 62 Rix arrivals performance.

	RUNWAY 18				RUNWAY 36			
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	11.60	3250	205	760	11.5	3300	192.5	722.5
FAP	7.40	2500	167.5	872.5	7.4	2500	165	860
FA 2000ft	6.40	2000	150	855	6.55	2000	142.5	865
FA 1000ft	3.35	1000	120	710	3.4	1000	125	717.5
LD 500ft	1.85	500	120	712.5	1.85	500	125	710
LD 0ft	0.45	0	80	0	0.6	0	112.5	0

Table 22. Rix arrivals performance data.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Average trajectories at RIX airport are shown in the following figure.

Figure 63 Average trajectories for RIX airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 64 Average departure trajectories for RIX airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 65 Average arrival trajectories for RIX airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

3.4.3 Barcelona

Since 20th April of 2023, RNAV is the only navigation method contemplated on standard instrument departures. The departure procedures depend on the destination, with eastbound and westbound departures available. Below will be detailed the departure procedures for each runway, starting with the eastern direction for each runway:

- **Runway 02:** Climb until reaching 500 ft or above and turn right. There are different options after the turn, depending on the destination. This runway is the preferred during night periods.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

- **Runway 06L.** There are two departures procedures: DNP and alternatives.

Figure 67. BCN departures procedures DNP (SID) runway 06L.

Figure 68. BCN departures procedures alternatives (SID) runway 06L.

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- **Runway 06L/06R**

Figure 78. BCN arrivals procedures alternatives (STAR) runway 06L/06R.

- **Runway 24L/24R**

Figure 79. BCN arrivals procedures alternatives (STAR) runway 24L/24R.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

In the case of Josep Tarradellas Barcelona-El Prat airport (LEBL), there are different transition procedure to final approach, which are detailed in the TRANS charts. After passing the IAF, the aircrafts begin the transition, but it is not always necessary to complete the entire path. Instead, aircraft will cross checkpoints, and when cleared for final approach, will turn out of the transition, and commence the approach. Each runway that allows for landing has its own specific procedure:

- **Runway 02**

Figure 80. BCN approach transition procedure (TRAN) runway 02.

- **Runway 06L**

Figure 81. BCN approach transition procedure (TRAN) runway 06L.

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- Runway 06R

Figure 82. BCN approach transition procedure (TRAN) runway 06R.

- Runway 24L

Figure 83. BCN approach transition procedure (TRAN) runway 24L.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

- Runway 24R

Figure 84. BCN approach transition procedure (TRAN) runway 24R.

Real data of flights that have departed and arrived at BCN airport have been processed. Average values have been obtained to observe the profile of the aircraft for a range of altitude for ground speed and vertical speed at certain points in vertical profile and the mean trajectory in lateral profile. The data are taken from the months June, July and August of 2022 year.

For departure procedures, the data is represented for each threshold that allows landing. The data used to represent the graph has also been added and is found in the following table.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 85 BCN departure performance.

RUNWAY 06L			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.0	0	135	0
1.6	500	165	1250
2.3	1000	160	2200
3.9	2000	185	1300
5.8	3000	210	1550
9.6	4000	240	2000
10.8	5000	260	1750
12.0	6000	280	1850
RUNWAY 06R			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.0	0	130	5
1.7	500	155	1400
2.1	1000	150	2250
3.5	2000	175	1700
4.9	3000	195	2050
6.9	4000	200	1850

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8.9	5000	150	2000
10.1	6000	260	2150
RUNWAY 24L			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.0	0	122.5	8
1.6	500	162.5	1375
2.1	1000	160	2375
3.4	2000	185	1450
5.0	3000	210	2000
6.7	4000	217.5	2150
9.1	5000	245	2400
10.7	6000	257.5	2350

Table 23. BCN departures performance data.

For arrivals procedures, the data is also represented for each threshold that allows takeoffs. In this case, the representative points are the IF, FAP, FA and LD, as in RIX airport. It should be highlighted that most of the runways in this airport has the FAP (Final Approach Point) around 2000ft, so the point FA 2000ft has been excluded. The data used to represent the graph has also been added and is found in the following table.

Figure 86 BCN arrivals performance.

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

RUNWAY 02				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	11.32	3000	215	700
FAP	6	1900	180	675
FA 1000ft	3	1000	150	800
LD 500ft	1.5	500	140	750
LD 0ft	0	0	125	325
RUNWAY 06L				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	12.44	3550	220	600
FAP	9	3100	200	650
FA 2000ft	6	2000	170	850
FA 1000ft	3	1000	145	750
LD 500ft	1.5	500	135	725
LD 0ft	0	0	130	425
RUNWAY 24L				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	9.7	2300	190	720
FAP	5.4	1800	165	850
FA 1000ft	3	1000	143	750
LD 500ft	1.5	500	135	650
LD 0ft	0	0	120	425
RUNWAY 24R				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	11	3000	205	650
FAP	6.9	2200	175	700
FA 1000ft	3.14	1000	145	750
LD 500ft	1.57	500	140	725
LD 0ft	0	0	130	375

Table 24. BCN arrivals performance data.

Figure 87 BCN Global mean trajectories performance.

Figure 88 BCN departure mean trajectories performance.

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Figure 89 BCN arrivals mean trajectories performance.

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- Runway 14R: two types of departure procedure depending on whether it is day or night.

Figure 92 MAD Diurnal departure SID Runway 14R

Figure 93 MAD Nocturnal departure SID Runway 14R

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

- Runway 36L: two types of departure procedure depending on whether it is day or night.

Figure 94 MAD Diurnal departure SID Runway 36L

Figure 95 MAD Nocturnal departure SID Runway 36L

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

- Runway 36R: two types of departure procedure depending on whether it is day or night.

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- STAR: For the arrival process the only navigation method contemplated on the standard instrument arrival is RNAV. For each of the 4 runways used to arrivals grouped in pairs, the procedures are different.
 - Runway 18L/18R

Figure 98 MAD Arrival STAR Runway 18L/18R

Figure 99 MAD Arrival STAR Runway 18L/18R

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

○ Runway 32L/32R

Figure 100 MAD Arrival STAR Runway 32L/32R

Figure 101 MAD Arrival STAR Runway 32L/32R

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Real data of flights that have departed and arrived at MAD airport have been processed. Average values have been obtained to observe the profile of the aircraft for a range of altitude for ground speed and vertical speed at certain points in vertical profile and the mean trajectory in lateral profile. The data are taken from the months June, July and August of 2022 year.

For departures, the data are presented for each threshold that allows landing. The data used to display the graph have also been added and are shown in the table below.

Figure 102 MAD Departure performance

RUNWAY 14L			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0.9	0	138	60,4
1.9	500	170.1	1.423,4
2.5	1000	168	2.313,7
3.8	2000	169	2.309,1
5.2	3000	175.9	1.992,5
RUNWAY 14R			
Distance	Altitude	Ground Speed	Vertical Speed

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

(NM)	(ft)	(kt)	(ft/min)
1,0	0	134,7	1,0
2,2	500	175,0	1.436,8
2,9	1000	174,2	2.074,7
4,4	2000	175,9	2.020,9
6,1	3000	181,0	1.752,2
RUNWAY 36L			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
1,1	0	152,2	29,7
2,1	500	172,3	1.250,9
2,7	1000	173,4	2.135,4
4,3	2000	180,9	1.990,6
5,7	3000	185,2	1.845,7
RUNWAY 36R			
Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
0,9	0	137,3	32,9
1,9	500	166,0	1.366,4
2,5	1000	164,9	2.217,4
3,8	2000	172,3	2.159,6
5,5	3000	179,2	1.900,4

Table 25: Madrid departures performance data.

For arrivals procedures, the data is also represented for each threshold that allows takeoffs. In this case, the representative points are the IF, FAP, FA and LD, as in the previous airports. It should be highlighted that most of the runways in this airport has the FAP (Final Approach Point) around 2000ft, so the point FA 2000ft has been excluded. The data used to represent the graph has also been added and is found in the following table.

For a better understanding of this graph, it should be noted that the significant points shown, such as IF or FAP, are different for each runway. This means that for the same distance from the threshold, a different altitude or vertical speed is found for each runway.

For instance, the STAR procedures commence further down the runway on runways 32L and 32R than on runways 18L or 18R. This is evident from the fact that the starting distance on runways 32L/32R is around 12 NM, whereas on the other two runways it is approximately 18 NM.

Figure 103 MAD Arrival performance

RUNWAY 18L				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	17,6	4078	220,9	534,2
FAP	12,2	4078	195,2	264,4
FA 2000ft	6	2000	177,6	916,0
FA 1000ft	3	1000	147,8	745,3
LD 500ft	1,5	500	141,8	738,2
LD 0ft	0	0	125,9	443,9
RUNWAY 18R				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	17	5000	214,8	892,3
FAP	14,9	5000	204,9	396,7
FA 2000ft	6	2000	174,3	876,3
FA 1000ft	3	1000	145,9	767,9
LD 500ft	1,5	500	142,3	725,0
LD 0ft	0	0	126,1	400,5
RUNWAY 32L				
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

IF	12,2	2867	233,4	1001,0
FAP	6,2	2067	212,7	410,1
FA 1000ft	3	1000	150,4	744,3
LD 500ft	1,5	500	143,7	760,2
LD 0ft	0	0	139,2	644,3
	RUNWAY 32R			
	Distance (NM)	Altitude (ft)	Ground Speed (kt)	Vertical Speed (ft/min)
IF	11,9	3220	216,5	912,1
FAP	9,4	3114	213,2	593,5
FA 2000ft	5,96	2000	181,7	1007,4
FA 1000ft	3	1000	148,6	799,1
LD 500ft	1,49	500	143,8	763,2
LD 0ft	0	0	138,3	619,5

Table 26: Madrid arrivals performance data.

Figure 104 MAD Global mean trajectories performance

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Figure 105 MAD Departure mean trajectories performance

Figure 106 MAD Arrival mean trajectories performance

4 Applicable laws for LAQ&N and specific regulations for airport environment

4.1 Dortmund

Regarding Dortmund Airport, there's no specific rule on noise pollution, yet there's a detailed guideline on noise emissions in Germany mentioned on this website:

[Bezirksregierung Münster – Lärm \(bezreg-muenster.de\)](http://bezirksregierung-muenster.de)

Type of acoustic area	Lday	Lnight
Industrial areas	70	70
Commercial site	65	50
Core areas, village areas, mixed areas	60	45
General residential areas, small housing estates	55	40
Residential area	50	35
Hospitals and nursing home	45	35

Table 27 Noise regulations for DTM airport

Specifically for Dortmund Airport, there isn't a dedicated regulation, yet there's a specific guideline on emissions in Germany mentioned on this website:

[BMU-IGI2-20210818-SF-A007 \(verwaltungsvorschriften-im-internet.de\)](http://verwaltungsvorschriften-im-internet.de)

Sulfur dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	350 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 24 times per calendar year)
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	24 hours	125 µg/m ³ ((shall not exceed more than 3 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _a)	1 year	50 µg/m ³

Table 28 Sulfur dioxide regulations for DTM airport

Nitrogen Oxide and nitrogen dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	200CO µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 18 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 29 Nitrogen Oxide and Dioxide regulations for DTM airport

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

PM₁₀:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	24 hours	50 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 35 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _a)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 30 PM₁₀ regulations for DTM airport

PM_{2.5}:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _a)	1 year	25 µg/m ³

Table 31 PM_{2.5} regulations for DTM airport

Lead:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _a)	1 year	0,5 µg/m ³

Table 32 Lead regulations for DTM airport

Benzene:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _a)	1 year	5 µg/m ³

Table 33 Benzene regulations for DTM airport

CO:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
The eight-hour limit for the protection of human health (R _a)	The maximum concentration of pollution during eight hours of the day	10 mg/m ³

Table 34 CO regulations for DTM airport

4.2 Riga

There are no specific rules for the airport. Limit values for noise is defined in Cabinet of ministers 07.01.2014 regulation Nr. 16 (<https://likumi.lv/ta/id/263882-troksna-novertesanas-un-parvaldibas-kartiba>) 2nd Annex. Noise limit values is defined differently by the type of main use of the territory. No limit values for L_{den} . Suggestion is to use limit values for Individual residential houses if only one limit value can be used.

	Lday	Levening	Lnight
Territory of individual (detached houses, low-rise or homesteads) residential houses, children's institutions, medical, health and social care institutions	55	50	45
Territory of multi-storey residential buildings	60	55	50
The territory of public construction (the territory of public and administrative objects, including the territory of cultural institutions, educational and scientific institutions, state and local government administrative institutions and hotels) (with residential construction)	60	55	55
The territory of mixed construction, including the territory of trade and service buildings (with residential construction)	65	60	55
Quiet areas in urban municipalities	50	45	40

Table 35 Latvia thresholds for noise

Type of area	2022, km ²
Territory of individual (detached houses, low-rise or homesteads) residential houses, children's institutions, medical, health and social care institutions	14,7
Territory of multi-storey residential buildings	0,6
The territory of public construction (the territory of public and administrative objects, including the territory of cultural institutions, educational and scientific institutions, state and local government administrative institutions and hotels) (with residential construction)	0,5
The territory of mixed construction, including the territory of trade and service buildings (with residential construction)	1,1
Others (nature, water, agricultural, industrial and transport) without limit values	70,3
Incl. nature areas	32,7
Incl. water bodies	3,2
Incl. Industrial and transport	28,8
Incl. agriculture	5,6
Kopā:	87,1

Table 36 Latvia type of areas

Limit values for LAQ is (at least final metrics):

INDIGO project has received funding from the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) under the Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement No 101096055.

Limit values is defined in Cabinet of ministers 03.11.20094 regulation Nr. 1290. (<https://likumi.lv/ta/id/200712-noteikumi-par-gaisa-kvalitati>)

Sulfur dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	200 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 18 times per calendar year)
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	24 hours	125 µg/m ³ ((shall not exceed more than three times per calendar year)

Table 37 Sulfur dioxide regulations for RIX airport

Nitrogen Oxide and nitrogen dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	350 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 24 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 38 Nitrogen Oxide and Dioxide regulations for RIX airport

PM₁₀:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	24 hours	50 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 35 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 39 PM₁₀ regulations for RIX airport

PM_{2.5}:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	20 µg/m ³

Table 40 PM_{2.5} regulations for RIX airport

Lead:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	0,5 µg/m ³

Table 41 Lead regulations for RIX airport

Benzene:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
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Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	5 µg/m ³
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Table 42 Benzene regulations for RIX airport

CO:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
The eight-hour limit for the protection of human health (R _d)	The maximum concentration of pollution during eight hours of the day	10 mg/m ³

Table 43 CO regulations for RIX airport

4.3 Barcelona

While there isn't a specific regulation in place for Barcelona's airport, there are established norms throughout Spain regarding noise emission limits. These limits are detailed according to each specific zone. All information described in official bulletin of the province of Barcelona in the modification of (02-05-2011): [Normativa – Mediciones de ruido | Sonometrias | Normativa ruido | Barcelona \(certificacioacustica.cat\)](#)

Acoustic sensitivity areas and land uses	Inmissions limit values in dB(A)		
	Lday	Levening	Lnight
HIGH ACUSTIC SENSITIVITY ZONE (A)			
Parks with special acoustic protection	-	-	-
Parks with special acoustic protection	55	55	45
Parks, gardens and beaches	57	57	47
Predominance of land for health, educational and cultural use	55	55	45
Predominance of land for residential use	60	60	50
MODERATE ACUSTIC SENSITIVITY ZONE (B)			
Coexisting of land for residential use with existing transport activities and/or infrastructure	65	65	55
Predominance of land for tertiary use different from (C1)	65	65	55
Existing urbanized areas affected by industrial land use	65	65	55
LOW ACUSTIC SENSITIVITY ZONE (C)			
(C1) Recreational and entertainment uses	68	68	58
Predominance of land for industrial use	70	70	60

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areas of the territory affected by general transport infrastructure systems or other public facilities that claim them	-	-	-
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Table 44 Noise regulations for BCN airport

Regarding gas emissions, Spain has established specific norms for different zones. At Barcelona's airport, while there isn't a distinct regulation, the country's overall guidelines on gas emissions apply.

Sulfur dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	350 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 24 times per calendar year)
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	24 hours	125 µg/m ³ ((shall not exceed more than 3 times per calendar year)

Table 45 Sulfur dioxide regulations for BCN airport

Nitrogen Oxide and nitrogen dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	200 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 18 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 46 Nitrogen Oxide and Dioxide regulations for BCN airport

PM₁₀:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	24 hours	50 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 35 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 47 PM₁₀ regulations for BCN airport

PM_{2.5}:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	25 µg/m ³

Table 48 PM_{2.5} regulations for BCN airport

Lead:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	0,5 µg/m ³

Table 49 Lead regulations for BCN airport

Benzene:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	5 µg/m ³

Table 50 Benzene regulations for BCN airport

CO:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
The eight-hour limit for the protection of human health (R _d)	The maximum concentration of pollution during eight hours of the day	10 mg/m ³

Table 51 CO regulations for BCN airport

4.4 Madrid

Similarly, in Madrid's airport, there isn't a specific regulation for both noise and gas emissions. However, Community of Madrid has established specific norms for different zones across the country regarding these aspects specifiend in the following website: [Límites de niveles sonoros emitidos al medio ambiente exterior - Ayuntamiento de Madrid](#)

Type of acoustic area	Lday	Levening	Lnight
Sectors of the territory with a predominance of land for health, educational and cultural use requiring special protection against noise pollution.	50	50	40
Sectors of the territory with a predominance of land for residential use.	55	55	45
Sectors of the territory with a predominance of land for tertiary use other than that referred to in c.	60	60	50
Sectors of the territory with a predominance of land for recreational and entertainment use.	63	63	53
Sectors of the territory with a predominance of land for industrial use	65	65	55

Table 52 Noise regulations for MAD airport

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Regarding gas emissions, Spain has established specific norms for different zones. At Madrid's airport, while there isn't a distinct regulation, the country's overall guidelines on gas emissions apply.

Sulfur dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	350 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 24 times per calendar year)
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	24 hours	125 µg/m ³ ((shall not exceed more than 3 times per calendar year)

Table 53 Sulfur dioxide regulations for MAD airport

Nitrogen Oxide and nitrogen dioxide

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Hourly limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	1 hour	200 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 18 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 54 Nitrogen Oxide and Dioxide regulations for MAD airport

PM₁₀:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Daily limit value for the protection of human health (R _h)	24 hours	50 µg/m ³ (shall not exceed more than 35 times per calendar year)
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	40 µg/m ³

Table 55 PM₁₀ regulations for MAD airport

PM_{2.5}:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	25 µg/m ³

Table 56 PM_{2.5} regulations for MAD airport

Lead:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	0,5 µg/m ³

Table 57 Lead regulations for MAD airport

Benzene:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
Annual limit value for the protection of human health (R _d)	1 year	5 µg/m ³

Table 58 Benzene regulations for MAD airport

CO:

Type of limit value	Time frame	Limit value
The eight-hour limit for the protection of human health (R _d)	The maximum concentration of pollution during eight hours of the day	10 mg/m ³

Table 59 CO regulations for MAD airport

5 Indicators derived from regulations to measure LAQ&N

At this point, the following indicators are proposed for the LAQ&N assessment as part of INDIGO project:

INDIGO indicators		
Area	Type	Indicator
Noise	SESAR-NOI	LDEN (noise perception): above 55dB (regarding regulation)
	SESAR-NOI4	Population exposed to an exceeded threshold (using official population values)
LAQ (emissions)	Gaseous emission (carbon)	CO
	Gaseous emission (env)	NOx
	Gaseous emission (HC)	VOC: MHC and non-MHC
	Gaseous emission (sulphur)	SOx (SO ₂)
	Particulate Matter	PM _{2.5/10} : volatile and non volatile
	Particulate Matter	Black Carbon

Table 60 INDIGO environmental indicators

All the proposed metrics can be measured with respect its reference threshold value for each UC and their stablished regulations, except for Black Carbon and VOC. Nevertheless, the maximum reduction will be always the objective for all pollutants. Furthermore, take into account that these thresholds are just a reference value for a specific point, it can be attributed to many other sources and factors other than aviation. Thus, this comparison is only from a legislative perspective.

6 Base LAQ stations measurement

This section provides an overview of the most critical pollutants of each airport selected. This will lead to the importance of each pollutant to be optimized during the analysis of most eco-friendly trajectories and also for the aircraft performance optimization process.

Note: DTM does not have any emissions station measurement near the airport or is not available, thus this analysis cannot be done. The common critical and most harmful pollutants will be applied in this case.

6.1 Riga

Results from the LAQ measurement stations show only 6 out 35 daily thresholds exceeding for the PM₁₀.

Figure 107 Daily Average PM₁₀ for RIX

The annual average value for the PM_{2.5} measurement is 9 micrograms/m³ (under the threshold of 25 µg/m³). For these reasons, it can be concluded that there is no evidence of high PM concentrations.

Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) hourly concentrations do not exceed the 350 µg/m³ threshold. There are not daily values registered over 125 µg/m³.

As for the Ozone, there is not any 8-hour value over the threshold either.

Figure 108 Daily Average O₃ for RIX

Finally, NO₂ hourly values are under 200 µg/m³ (the maximum registered is 131 µg/m³), and the average annual value is 20 µg/m³ (under the maximum and critical concentration levels).

Nevertheless, it is highly recommended to optimize the engine NO_x emissions (especially NO₂ emissions) in order to reduce these values, that could be higher in the surroundings of Riga airport.

6.2 Barcelona

There are some episodes of high NO_x concentrations (in micrograms/m³) measured near Barcelona – El Prat airport:

Baix Llobregat	12	18	30	24	25	30	54	53	74	76	75	34	21	35	25	9	6	11	12	10	27	25	14	13
Baix Llobregat	9	9	10	15	24	28	28	22	35	21	29	24	15	12	6	9	10	10	10	11	13	8	6	32
Baix Llobregat	18	10	18	20	17	28	25	27	25	9	13	20	23	18	15	11	12	11	11	14	16	12	13	12
Baix Llobregat	11	19	23	32	38	57	67	135	101	49	28	21	16	18	15	15	12	18	9	11	9	16	10	37
Baix Llobregat	35	21	30	29	32	37	63	121	106	27	23	23	25	17	16	13	9	11	17	27	29	29	22	31
Baix Llobregat	16	26	29	32	36	56	88	126	107	22	28	12	12	8	5	6	5	4	12	9	5	6	9	11
Baix Llobregat	12	12	12	19	25	40	76	113	72	51	45	16	20	13	16	11	11	10	10	10	10	11	12	11
Baix Llobregat	23	27	27	29	27	35	36	53	54	47	39	29	19	15	12	16	12	7	6	7	9	11	12	10
Baix Llobregat	16	18	11	21	29	22	24	16	13	14	18	13	11	6	5	6	4	4	4	10	8	12	12	15
Baix Llobregat	28	12	3	4	5	26	83	104	166	159	109	64	58	17	6	8	9	8	10	16	19	19	31	54
Baix Llobregat	52	27	26	44	54	48	58	94	111	102	64	45	14	6	5	2	3	5	9	11	13	12	28	53
Baix Llobregat	5	3	8	12	10	15	12	57	51	31	33	25	17	9	11	4	3	5	36	43	18	6	15	5
Baix Llobregat	5	18	28	36	32	40	46	66	70	57	19	14	22	15	6	2	4	13	12	10	14	7	8	31
Baix Llobregat	48	38	30	26	27	37	54	107	149	138	32	16	24	8	5	2	4	7	6	8	7	9	64	60
Baix Llobregat	47	50	43	33	38	36	39	57	34	89	44	14	9	2	1	2	1	2	3	6	5	2	4	2
Baix Llobregat	2	1	1	1	1	3	5	1	3	10	12	3	3	1	1	1	2	8	12	5	1	1	1	4

Figure 109 NO_x values for BCN

For this reason, it is recommended to optimize the engine NO_x emissions to reduce these values.

6.3 Madrid

From the LAQ reports, there is no evidence of any threshold exceeding except to the Ozone 8-hour values at three measurement stations:

Figure 110 O₃ values for MAD

However, from the annual reports published by AENA airports, it does not seem to be directly related to the Adolfo Suárez – Madrid Barajas airport activities:

Figure 111 O₃ values for MAD airport

In any case, it is highly recommended to optimize the engine NO_x emissions (especially NO₂ emissions as O₃ precursors) in order to reduce these values and improve the LAQ in Madrid city and surroundings.

7 Annex A

Full list of considered Use Cases.

Catalogue of
UC_Candidates select

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